

ADVANCE SOCIAL SCIENCE ARCHIVE JOURNAL

Available Online: <https://assajournal.com>

Vol. 04 No. 02. October-December 2025. Page# 2991-3006

Print ISSN: [3006-2497](#) Online ISSN: [3006-2500](#)

Platform & Workflow by: [Open Journal Systems](#)

Transitivity Analysis in the Statement of Former Prime Minister Imran Khan on Pulwama Attack

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Abstract

In Systemic Functional Linguistics, transitivity analysis systematically explores how language functions in a particular setting and how meanings are produced at the discourse level. The current study aimed to explore hidden meanings, ideologies and power relations in the Official Statement of Prime Minister Imran Khan issued on the Pulwama Attack. The Pulwama attack was a part of India's false flag operation to exploit the commencement of an international event in Pakistan during February, 2019. Primarily, the research pertinently highlights denying proclamation with evidence and offering investigation to neighbours after the provision of actionable evidence. The study was conducted following a qualitative research methodology. The data sample of the Official Statement of the Prime Minister was acquired from the Official website of the Prime Minister's Office. For data analysis of the official statement of the PM, Halliday's ideational meta-function was selected as a theoretical framework and the UAM Corpus-based tool. Ver 6.2 was utilized for a clause-level analysis. Moreover, to explore the transitive. The findings of the research study revealed that types of processes, participants and circumstances are embedded in layers of the crafted text. Further, the analysis revealed that Prime Minister, Imran Khan used mantel and material types of transitivity in his Official Statement to deny from false flag Operation, formally invited for investigations and issued an ultimatum to retaliate in case of international breach.

Keywords: Ideational meta-function, Transitivity analysis, Official Statement, Pulwama Attack, UAM Corpus Tool

Introduction

Rapid transition in the formal approaches towards language exploration diverts the intention of the readers towards the meaning-making process. The functional approach towards language was formerly developed by M.A.K Halliday to study the metafunctions of languages. The meta functions in the language developed multilayered interpretations that can only be explored by implementing Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) approach. Implicit exploration of text facilitates the target audience to seek in-depth knowledge connected with national and public interest. With the evolution of the modern genres like official statements, informal discussions and press releases, researchers are introduced to novice quality of text. The formal statements issued from the government departments set new standards for the target audience to interact within the community and to choose the direction of their upcoming projects. Mainly, the nation and its inhabitants must remain aware of the ever-changing geo strategic situation and impacts of the incidents happening in their surroundings. The general awareness and public knowledge are mainly influenced and sharpened by the use of technology. Technology has a direct influence on improving pedagogical practices, acquiring specific information and promoting authentic learning (Ekanayake & Wishart, 2014).

Advanced Stylistics, an interdisciplinary branch of linguistics, formerly introduced a novice framework to study language equipped with layered meanings, frequently present in the text simultaneously. The study of the language/text through the lens of transitivity, frequently depicts various processes, participants and circumstances responsible for producing specific meanings and conveying ideologies to the target audience. The presence of various transitivity processes in the Official statements has transformed the field of public relations, politics and diplomacy. The variable use of the transitivity processes in the official statement of the former Prime Minister of Pakistan brings national harmony, cohesion and strengthens our resolve. The research study was mainly focused on the transitivity involved in shaping the formal statement of the former Prime Minister of Pakistan, Imran Khan. In a conventional setting, formal statements from the Prime Minister were considered as a fuel for media houses, political and military talks. Primarily, language is considered a humanistic trait and a tool for social interaction, basically designed for communicative and expressive functions. It involves meanings in multilayered settings explored through various frameworks. Initially, text was explored through literal meanings, but afterwards multiple meanings of the same text were explored using Halliday's SFL. Leech (1981), in his book Semantics: The study of meaning had also provided various categories of meanings.

The transitivity is a complex term crafted through various processes, including material, mental, existential, verbal and relational processes. It also considers the participants involved in the course, their socio-cultural and socio-economic background, power relations between speaker and audience. Transitivity analysis of the text also considers the circumstances for creation of text and its influence throughout the text. In transitivity analysis, mainly text is diluted with material process which provides details for certain happening and subsequent doing/actions by the actors involved in the process. Further, the mental process provides a glimpse of cognitive abilities and sensorimotor abilities to judge the phenomena. The mental process directly

involving consciousness and human perception. The verbal process in the transitivity analysis provides account of the physical activity showing proper speaking or communication activity held at any instant within the text properly recognizing the speaker and the target audience. Further, the participants / actors involved in the communication and details of their relationship was described through relational process. The relational process was analysed to interpret specific properties of the participants/material involved in the discourse process. Further, bridging of the mental and material capabilities is accomplished through analysing the behaviour of the participants. Finally, the existential process provides evidence of an existing gap / problem account to initiate such discourse /text. The participants and their relation in the social process were also discussed, and their role was interpreted during analysis to assess their personal traits, related phenomena's and specific role in the context. In the final stage of the transitivity analysis, circumstances-based additional or auxiliary information was also added for better interpretation. Primarily, formal statements from the state offices were issued to understand the strength of diplomatic relations. However, official statements were also issued to counter false flag operations and to justify allegations lacking evidence. In the field of linguistics, particularly in advanced stylistics, formal statements were explored to analyse the transitivity processes involved in shaping the perceptions of common people and to neutralise anti-state agenda. In the Pakistani context, limited research was accomplished in exploring the official statements issued from the state offices and government sectors (Al-Maashani, 2023; Ali et al., 2024; Chigbu et al., 2025; Guswita & Suhardi, 2020; Iqbal et al., 2023; Kashif et al., 2022; Majeed & Zahra, 2021). The limited research conducted on the official statements issued from the Prime Minister Office, therefore, creates a valid gap to understand and interpret transitivity processes. The current study will be studied through transitivity analysis to identify the transitivity process to explore the meanings conveyed through the official statement.

1.1 Research Objectives

- 1.1.1 To determine the transitivity processes in the Statement of PM Imran Khan issued on the incident of the Pulwama Attack.
- 1.1.2 To explore the frequent transitivity process that shapes the text of the Statement of PM Imran Khan.
- 1.1.3 To explore the meaning / set of ideologies conveyed through the statement of the PM.

1.2 Research Questions

- 1.2.1 What are the transitivity processes involved in the statement of the PM Imran Khan issued on the incident of the Pulwama Attack?
- 1.2.2 What are the frequent transitivity processes that shape the speech of PM Imran Khan?
- 1.2.3 What were specific meanings / ideologies were conveyed through the Statement of the PM Imran Khan

The official statements from the Government official is noteworthy from multiple perspectives providing insights to different strategic developments in the region. The interpretation and in-depth analysis facilitates comprehension of contextual meaning and auxiliary information. Moreover, the study has enabled readers to understand specific ideologies conveyed through these formal statements, thus providing a broader scope for

the research study. The study offers a new direction to novice researchers to explore official statements issued from various government officials

Literature Review

Prof Emeritus M.A.K Halliday's, a theorist and pioneer of Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL), provides a functional approach to explore language through its meta-functions. In structuralism and the generativist approach, transitivity referred to the syntactic construction of the text that directly impacts language through its form and structure, neglecting semantic and functional aspects of the language. A simple Verb-Object distinction was transformed into functional and semantic roles through Halliday's functional approach towards language, labelled as transitivity analysis. A foundational work, "An Introduction to Functional Grammar" facilitates understanding transitivity as the integration of different processes in the language and basic structure for their expression (Halliday, 1985). In this book, Halliday's developed Functional Grammar (FG), a well-constructed functional model under the domain of Systemic Functional Linguistics to consider grammar as meaning making inventory rather than a tool for syntactic construction. The Functional Grammar approach posits that specific language choice impacts readers and serves a specific purpose in the discourse.

In linguistics, transitivity analysis is a systematic process to explore how specific language choices represent actions, events, states and participants integrated in a discourse to reveal how a text creates impact on its audience, constructs meanings, facilitates point of view, characterization and builds ideologies through narrative. The transitivity analysis primarily focused on various process types (material, mental, relational, verbal, behavioural and existential), participants involved in the text or discourse (actor, goals, medium of communication) and emphasized the contextual situation (time, manner, cause, plane, etc) that actually shapes the readers' interpretation of a text. In detailed, three meta-functions of the language were proposed includes ideational meta-function (Logical & Experience relations), interpersonal meta-function (Mood, modality, Socio-cultural and socio-plotical relations between the participants) and textual meta-function (theme, rheme, Cohesion and Coherence). An introduction of Functional Grammar, 4th Edition a collaborative work of Halliday & Matthiessen was published in 2014 provide a detailed account of these functions. In the recent publication, descriptive approach is mainly focused to explore clause, main unit in the analysis process (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2013).

In 1979, Roger Fowler and a group of linguists (Bob Hodge, Gunther Kress, and Tony Trew), known as the "Critical Linguistics Group" co-authored a book, "Language and Control" that pertinently explores political text to showcase how specific language choices represent power relations and assist in evaluating bias ness in the text (Fowler et al., 1979). Through transitivity analysis, it was revealed that language is not a neutral element, specific lexical and syntactic choices shape ideology. Furthermore, the approach is utilized in Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA). Fairclough, Wodak and Leeuwen implemented transitivity analysis in Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) to examine power relations, socio-political inequality, press and media presentation of the major incidents and institutional discourse through official press releases, formal or informal statements issued from State Offices and narrative build by key figures. Leech & Short, (1981) explore characterization and point of view in fictional works to represent psychological states of the characters mind, foregrounding and narrator position

and point of view in the fiction. In the same manner, Paul Simpson provides literary analysis of the fictional text using transitivity analysis and provides a detailed account in his publication Simpson's Stylistics (1993).

Geoff Thompson, in his book *Introducing Functional Grammar* (1993), widely expands the effective area of transitivity analysis, facilitates refinement to meta-functions purely builds on the works of M.A.K Halliday meta-functions to reveal ideologies. In his research paper and pedagogical development. Thompson, (2008) provides a three-step approach to analyze transitivity concordance, transitivity templates and reveal ideology patterns. His approach was highly effective student in the academic environment to explore discourse and literature.

Prof Ronald Allan Carter, introduced discourse stylistics in his PhD dissertation and laid down foundation for future studies. In his most celebrated works, including *Language and Literature* (1982), *Exploring Literature* (1996) and *Working with Text* (1998), Ronald Carter utilizes transitivity analysis to explore how authors allocate agency in the text and the ideological positioning of the characters reflected through conceded events.

2.1 Advanced Stylistics

Advanced stylistics systematically explores the author's choice of language or speech uttered by a speaker including lexicology, grammar, syntax structure and discourse. Moreover, primarily advanced stylistics interpret how and to what extent specific language choices / piece of writing influence readers' perception, stimulate emotions and overall impact of the language. Stylistics refers to the study of text, unpacking distinctive styles of literary genres and writings (Mathe, 2024). Advanced stylistics includes material from both literary and non-literary fields, including advertisements, legal documents, formal or informal speeches or statements.

2.2 Systematic Functional Linguistics (SFL)

Michael Halliday developed the language theory of Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL). SFL explores how language impacts and creates meanings within the social context. Primarily SFL, consider grammar as a significant source for the creation of meanings and emphasizes the relationship of text with the corresponding social context. Michael Halliday, a well-known British linguist. He described language as a social activity that involves signs for meanings (Almurashi, 2016). SFL considers language as part of a contextualized semiotic system and is based on functional elements. Further, the function of language was divided owing to the strands of meanings, associated with the social context/situation defined through field, tenor and mode recognized as meta-functions. Ideational, Interpersonal and textual are the three meta-functions of language.

2.3 Ideational Meta-Function & Transitivity Analysis

Ideational meta-function of the language assists individuals/researchers to express human experience and perceived expression of reality both internally and externally. In the ideational meta-function, transitivity analysis is quite convenient and beneficial analysis tool to understand experiential meanings embedded in the text coherently. Transitivity analysis is a distinctive concept for the depiction of reality in various social contexts. The researcher is capable of revealing the thoughts of characters/individuals by implementing transitivity analysis, and also contributes to comprehending the text. In transitivity analysis, language permits the user to interpret the external world through various processes, including Material Process, Mental Process, Verbal Process, Relational Process, Behavioural Process and Existential Process. Primarily, the function of a clause is to

explore and signify individual experience and state of mind related to events / the external world. The specific analytical tool of transitivity analysis assists novice researchers to comprehend how language creates ideologies, themes and in-depth meanings in various literary and non-literary genres.

2.4 Review of Related Studies

Kashif et al., (2022) investigate three debates of American Presidential Candidates, Hilary Clinton and Donald Trump, prior to the commencement of the 2016 general election, to identify and interpret choice among the verbal groups using transitive analysis as a research tool. Halliday, Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) provide a theoretical framework for the research study. The researcher explores and identifies embedded stimulus, approaches and transitivity choice frequency through implementing the ideational meta-function of the SFL. The analysis of the study revealed that Donald Trump utilized 51% whereas 41% of the process was utilised in their debate sessions. The frequent utilization of verbal process mirrored an obvious and concrete viewpoint on the key problems facing the USA. Further, variation in transitivity choices of the political leaders was intended to attain public consent.

Guswita & Suhardi, (2020) investigate male and female variations in media discourse through transitivity analysis. To achieve the desired research objectives, Halliday's ideational function of language was utilized through analyzing transitivity elements in the specific genre. The literature review reveals that language in media discourse was highly affected by gender variation. Specifically in article writing, limited research was conducted. Mixed methodology was adopted to explore various processes to achieve enhanced understanding. T-test and Paired Sample have also been utilized to investigate significant differences owing to gender variation. The findings of the research study revealed no significant difference in media discourse and material process has been considered a recurring process. Further participant process provides more pertinent and in-depth data for further research.

Iqbal et al., (2023) explored elements of transitivity in the speech of the former Prime Minister delivered at the United Nations General Assembly (UNGA). The research mainly revealed how the Prime Minister of Pakistan laid emphasis on the ideology of Islamophobia and raised a democratic voice for the resolution of the Kashmir issue. For this research study, a quantitative research methodology was utilized. The transcription of Imran Khan's speech was used as a sample data. The theoretical framework was acquired through Halliday's ideational function of language and the analytical tool of a corpus-based tool was used to analyze the process of transitivity at the clause level. The findings of the research study revealed that the Prime Minister, Imran Khan, frequently utilized material type of transitivity to deliver speech effectively and to highlight the major issues of the region as well as of the Muslim community.

Al-Maashani (2023) investigated the speech of King Charles III inauguration speech delivered to the public of the UK and Commonwealth nations conveying affirmation of his designated role as King, to commemorate and mourned his mother. The theoretical framework for the study is provided through Systemic Functional Grammar theory by Halliday to reveal transitivity analysis in the Speech and to highlight the most frequent process of transitivity utilized in his speech. UAM Software was utilized to investigate the speech corpus and the analysis of the study revealed frequent use of material and mental processes along with

deliberate use of rational and verbal processes. The material clauses dominantly affirm King's determination and solemnity towards his new role. He promised to serve the people of the UK and Commonwealth countries.

Methodology

Methodology is primarily concerned with the systematic exploration of a research problem on the basis of an available data sample and interpreting valuable insights through the utilization of a theoretical and analytical framework. According to Patel and Patel (2019), "research methodology is the science of studying how research is done scientifically." The current study was based on the transitivity analysis of an official statement issued by the former Prime Minister of Pakistan, Imran Khan, on the Pulwama attack that occurred in February, 2019. The qualitative research of the Official statement of PM was analyzed through transitivity analysis grounded in Halliday's Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL). The research process indicated the various processes of transitivity actively involved in shaping the language choices for official statement and meanings / ideologies communicated through frequent transitivity processes.

The transitivity analysis of the Official Statement was conducted by implementing a qualitative research approach and adopting a descriptive research design to describe the various transitivity processes and the interpretation of meanings. Primarily, the basic purpose of the study is to explore the novice text of the official statement through the lens of transitivity analysis for analyzing its various processes, participants and circumstances. The transitivity analysis explores the specific meanings conveyed through the statement. Moreover, the set of ideologies communicated through the text of the statement was the main concern of the current study. The appropriate interpretation of various transitivity processes aids in informing the target audience about the intentions for neighbours, justifying blame and proactive defensive measures adopted to retaliate any misconduct.

The Official Statement of the former Prime Minister of Pakistan, Imran Khan issued on 19 February, 2019 taken as sample data, available at Official website of Prime Minister Office. The Official Statement was issued after five days of the incident and published through print media (English & Urdu Newspapers) electronic media (News Channels) and Social media platforms (Twitter). The Official Statement was comprising of 687 words, strongly condemning allegations imposed by the hostile country, India. The research was conducted in Nov-Dec, 2025 and the Prime Minister Office Official website was considered the most reliable source to acquire the Official Statement. However, the same has been published on various platforms as mentioned earlier. The transitivity process explored the underlying process actively involved in shaping the statement, participants involved and the influence of the various circumstances for issuance of the statement. Using UAM Corpus tool was utilized to find keywords list and keywords in context.

Sampling methods are categorized into probability or non-probability methods (Omair, 2014). In a research process, sampling assists in selecting relevant data, determining the participants involved in the research process and the variables involved in the research. The current study was conducted using a purposive sampling technique, a non-probability sampling technique that facilitates researcher in terms of time efficient manner of selecting data, cost-effective, reliable source for data collection and the most adaptable sampling technique.

The transitivity analysis of the Official statement of the former prime minister was a qualitative research with the specific purpose to identify various transitivity processes involved in shaping the Official statement, interpret underlying meanings and ideologies that impact people's perceptions and develop understanding towards the role of the state in defending false flag allegations and a proactive defensive approach. The research study was accomplished using Halliday's Systemic Functional Linguistics. Using online tools, sampled data of the Official statement of the former PM, Imran Khan, in the MS Word file (.doc) format, converted to a plain text file (.txt), and non-linguistic material was removed, including images, unwanted spaces / symbols, formal layouts, formats, designs, numerical tabulated data, hyperlinks and comments.

Figure 1 : UTF-8 BOM (.txt) file

UAM Corpus tool 6.2 was utilized for further analysis. In the UAM Software, the primarily developed corpus (.txt) was uploaded, and the text file was saved. Further, a layer was created using a manual annotation scheme. Further, clause-by-clause analysis was accomplished to identify transitivity processes utilized to shape the speech of the Former Prime Minister of Pakistan. In order to maintain the reliability of the research process and to avoid intentional misconduct, plagiarism and associated factors, the researcher is

considered solely responsible for a transparent research process. The researcher must protect the rights of the agencies involved in crafting the Official Statement and avoid judgmental commentary owing to various socio-political affiliations or to divert the attention of the readers. Moreover, the PM Office and the Official Statement from the former Prime Minister of Pakistan were representations of the whole nation, the researcher has to avoid their manipulation as they carry broader perspectives for the nation. The ethical elements of deception and false findings are considered to be a serious social as well as moral offence. The research and researcher must be capable of producing truthful findings based on research evidence that actually fits into its research gap in a persuasive manner. The development of AI tools in the 21st century has initiated modern threats to the stream of knowledge and pertinently developed ethical responsibility towards cyber security. The use of online platforms for data collection and AI tools for their statistical analysis must undergone cyber security protocols. The research conducted on the official statements from the state offices, press releases from the military institutions and informal talks of state official must be dealt with extreme care, strictly avoid hate speech and anti-state mind set.

4. Analysis and Discussion

The UAM tool-based analysis of the Official Statement of the former Prime Minister Imran Khan on the Pulwama Attack revealed that transitivity processes were frequently involved in shaping the text. Moreover, for better interpretation and deeper understanding of the analysis data was presented in a tabulated format. During the analysis, the ideational meta function, its various types and subtypes were explored using the UAM Corpus tool. Initially, keywords and frequency were analysed to overview content of the officially statement. The ratio and percentage are tabulated for enhanced interpretation and to show transparency in the results. The results revealed after the analysis process were displayed in the tables provide below.

4.1 Data Analysis

Table 1 : Keywords Analysis

Word	N (Text)	% (Text)	N (Ref.corp.)	% (Ref.corp.)	Propensity	ChiSqu	Log.Lik.	sqrt(Prop*ChiSqr)
pakistan	18	0.02628	0	0	100	99999999	NaN	99498.74
acts	5	0.0073	0	0	100	99999999	NaN	99498.74
terrorism	8	0.01168	0	0	100	99999999	NaN	99498.74
india	5	0.0073	0	0	100	99999999	NaN	99498.74

Table 2 : Frequency

Word	Count	Frequency
pakistan	18	0.026277372262773723
terrorism	8	0.01167883211678832
acts	5	0.0072992700729927005
india	5	0.0072992700729927005
think	4	0.00583941605839416
such	4	0.00583941605839416
indian	4	0.00583941605839416
dialogue	4	0.00583941605839416
new	4	0.00583941605839416
benefit	3	0.004379562043795621

Grammatical Ranks

During the analysis process, the grammatical ranks represent the information as tabulated below:-

Table 3 : Grammatical Ranks

GRAMMATICAL-RANK	N	%
- participant	142	32.1
- process	113	25.6
- circumstance	75	17.0
- configuration	97	21.9
- configuration-complex	0	0.0
TOTAL:	427	96.6%

In the current study, clause-level analysis was accomplished using Halliday’s Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) approach. The tabulated data depicted a total of 427 grammatical units utilized by the former Prime Minister, constituting 96.6% of the complete statement. Former PM, Imran Khan, confidently refuted Indian false flag allegations on Pakistan for being responsible for the Pulwama attack. All aspects of the grammar were keenly utilized to facilitate the depiction of a vivid picture to strategically defend the narrative of Pakistan.

Example

Table 4 : Clause Type

CLAUSE-TYPE	N	%
- material	46	10.4
- mental	20	4.5
- verbal	9	2.0
- relational	19	4.3
- modal	0	0.0
- existential	2	0.5
TOTAL:	96	21.7%
Uncoded:	1	-

In the current study, clause-level analysis revealed dominant utilization of material, mental and relational clauses within the official statement of the Former PM. A high percentage of material clauses revealed a focused and ideological representation in the statement. Further, the clause-level analysis revealed the involvement of physical action and occurrences.

Table 5 : Material Type

MATERIAL-TYPE	N	%
- intransitive	12	2.7
- monotransitive	31	7.0
- ergative	2	0.5
- ditransitive	1	0.2
TOTAL:	46	10.4%

Mostly material verb types were frequently utilized in the official statement of the PM. Further, it was revealed that doing and happenings include the material process (Halliday & Mathiessen, 2004). According to Wang (2010), usually material process usually comprises two participants (actor & agent).

Table 6 : Mental Type

MENTAL-TYPE	N	%
- cognition	0	0.0
- perception	0	0.0
- reaction	0	0.0
TOTAL:	0	0.0%
Uncoded:	20	-

MENTAL-TYPE2	N	%
- mental-active	19	4.3
- mental-passive	1	0.2
TOTAL:	20	4.5%

During clause-level analysis, mental processes were directly involved in shaping the official statement. A specific ideology and set of perceptions had been conveyed in the statement blaming India for false flag allegations, lacking evidence, and reality is interpreted through facts.

Table 7 : Verb Type

VERBAL-TYPE	N	%
- addressee-oriented	0	0.0
- not-addressee-oriented	0	0.0
TOTAL:	0	0.0%
Uncoded:	9	-

VERBAL-TYPE2	N	%
- verbal-active	7	1.6
- verbal-passive	2	0.5
TOTAL:	9	2.0%

Table 8 : Relational Type

RELATIONAL-TYPE	N	%
- identifying	0	0.0
- attributive	15	3.4
- circumstantial	0	0.0
- possessive	2	0.5
TOTAL:	17	3.8%
Uncoded:	2	-

The verbal type clauses were often utilized for the construction of authorial voice to announce, counter and to declare specific action in the given circumstances to handle socio-political situations. The processes of being are included in Relational Processes (Halliday, 2009).

4.2 Discussion

In the current study, Halliday's SFL function approach towards discourse text was utilized through transitivity analysis to explore layered meanings. The Official Statement of the Prime Minister, Imran Khan issued on 19 February, 2019 to counter illegal allegations and diplomatic tension escalated after suicide terrorist attack on the Central Reserve Police Force (CRPF) convoy in Pulwama on 14 February, 2019 while travelling from Jammu towards Srinagar. The Official statement was issued that directly denied Pakistan's contribution in the terrorism and latest terrorist activities on Indian military. The allegations lacking evidence and Former PM invited to share actionable evidence through a strategic dialogue. The Former PM clearly cautioned against any military retaliation and violation of the international boundaries as Pakistan always favoured to maintain regional and global peace. The statement conveyed state decision in a well-organized manner.

Former PM Imran Khan statement a strict notice regarding Indian allegations. However, the response was communicated after the culmination of the Investment Conference and departure of the Crown Prince from Saudi Arabia. The statement blames Indian government lacking evidence against Pakistan involvement in terrorists' activities. Pakistan is a peace seeking country and had no interest in such activities as the nation losses 70,000 lives of military and civilian personnel owing to the terrorist activities in the region since 2001. Mainly material, mental and relational processes were frequently utilised in shaping the statement (Ahmad, 2019). In the official statement process, participants, circumstances, and configuration are the main components (Qasim et al., 2018). At the clause level analysis, material and mental processes were strongly applied. The use of material process in the statement of the former PM Imran Khan as influential leader and political personality provides an overview of the false flag allegations and hidden perspectives of the neighboring country.

5. Conclusion

The transitivity analysis of the official statement of the former PM Imran Khan issued on the counter to Indian allegations against Pakistan revealed material and mental processes frequently. The utilization of UAM Software Ver 6.2 for data analysis and interpretation genuinely standardize the findings. The findings revealed that various transitivity processes involved in the statement and clause level interpretation provide specific meanings / convey ideologies to shift the perceptions of the public. The official statement facilitates a multidisciplinary audience, resulting in developing harmony for the national interest. The findings of the study facilitate linguists, ESP / EOP professionals, and curriculum developers in the preparation of the specific content.

The research study has significant theoretical and pedagogical implications for novice researchers as it facilitates methodology to explore official statements issued by the Government Offices and officials. Moreover, the study attracts ESP / EOP learners and professionals in crafting specific texts and in the development of writing skills. Additionally, the study offers implications for defence analysts, media houses, journalists, spokespersons and ambassadors to defend the established narrative. The interpretation aids in conveying specific meanings/ideologies through statements. The transitivity analysis offers guidelines to policy makers, management & faculty members of higher education to add specific content as a part of the curriculum. Finally, the study provides a soft image of the country and national efforts towards the attainment of global peace. The current study also offers future recommendations for researchers to conduct studies with an enhanced sample size and an increase in the time frame. In the same context, interviews conducted with the key officials of the country may also be analysed through the same methodology.

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